

MIMS 2.6.1 : Shi 勢

A short look at an ancient multidimensional model

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ABSTRACT

In several EPEMC papers, the use of the Chinese word “shi” has been made reference to, for the simple reason that in discussion of strategy, nothing else can more succinctly explain the concept. It is a word without a good translation. Is this word - a model of something really - also a MIMS? In this paper we examine the 8 layers of complexity and compare against the previous model for MIMS diagramming.

Keywords: MIMS - strategy - art of war

An ancient model

Shi has been translated by Giles to be “the strategic configuration of power.”¹ But Julien has translated it as “propensity.”² The author has taken the preference in his own chess³ and strategy texts^{4 5} to use “positional advantage.” All of these rely upon strategic or Newtonian mechanisms, particularly momentum and inertia, and vectors in general, to describe a situation of movement and relationship. The author in a separate work described it as a multidimensional field of relationship.⁶

From a physics perspective, there is not only the concept of the vector and attendant mechanistic and kinetic energies to consider, but also the potential energy, charge, and even probability. The word, therefore, was a model which gave some leeway to a multipurpose utility. Yet it had the precision and accuracy to describe the “energy” of armies, cities, nations, and the general tendency of how things would/should turn out. This is not easy to accomplish, although Chinese language has several such words.⁷

Choosing a concise list of definitions

For the purposes of this analysis, we will list very limited definitions for Shi. The table will provide a compounding expansion of the model. Each new pair of layers will be potential additions, not necessarily requirements.

	Level 1		Level 3
Tendency/Momentum Structure/Configuration		Timing Spatiality	
	Level 2		Level 4
Potential/Charge/Tension Position		Probability/Propensity Inertia	

Most of these terms are concise enough to the reader. By timing the author means to explain that the Shi is known to expand, contract, and all success to depend upon the Changes themselves. “Miss it by an inch, miss it by a mile.”

By probability the author means that a cloud of potentiality, possibility, and probability collapse into a single reality. Technically, this is more the concept of Ji 機, however, the two are inextricably related. The Shi produces the Ji.⁸

¹ <http://classics.mit.edu/Tzu/artwar.html>

² “The Propensity of Things,” F. Jullien, 1995

³ https://www.academia.edu/40287817/Understanding_Chess_I_The_Art_of_Chess

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https://www.academia.edu/49950880/CALCULATING_THE_INNATE_SHI_%E5%8B%A2_OF_COUNTRIES_USING_THE_UNITED_STATES_OF_AMERICA_AS_A_TEMPLATE_1

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https://www.academia.edu/49950881/Asymmetric_Vulnerabilities_of_the_US_and_New_Capabilities_in_Geopolitical_Warfare_Including_Economic_Digital_Cyberspatial_and_Lawfare

⁶ Ibid. pp. 5

⁷ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1j9pBwAonLP__qH5TYoQ-EOm23UI93sKW6gN1pM1Bipw/edit?usp=sharing

⁸ Ibid. pp. 9

By spatiality the author means that the structure itself creates rippling effects upon the Shi field, and can determine or affect outcomes. Typical examples include sports, boxing, battle arrays⁹, naval and air battalion arrangements¹⁰, etc.

MIMS Model conformity

The author has already pre-arranged these layers to work within the model. So let us briefly discuss why each is yang or yin.

- Momentum is yang precisely because it is active, literally mass moving at a velocity (a vector).
- Structure and configuration is yin because it is material, or crystalline
- Potential is yang because it is invisible. Charge because it is electric. Tension because it is on the ‘anger’ spectrum.¹¹
- Position is yin because it is indicative of relative difference between objects.
- Timing is yang because it relates to the Aether’s changes and flux.
- Spatiality is yin because, like position, it indicates relative arrangement of objects.
- Probability is yang because it is potential; Propensity is yang because it is momentum.
- Inertia is yin because it is resistive and dissonant to change.

Please note that none of this has any gender designation at all.

Discussion

The layering of the model is intended to increase the value of the model, and not to decrease it through distractive concepts. What is important is that the above flows down to the bottom, whether it is 2, 4, 6, or 8 layers etc. This is a classic MIMS model¹². We see that what is being materialized is an explanation for a sense of something in the “aether” or detected by the “mind” but not so easily measured or described. One knows one’s place in life, or position, or one is reminded of it by being weakened. If one knows it, then one can strengthen oneself by improving it.

Why is the MIMS so effective? It does not appear to be describable in a block diagram, but it does conform to hypothesis (I) from MIMS 2.0: it is infinite but definite. Infinite because of the relativity, field relationships, and continual adjusting of all values. Definite because it is, in the end surmise, quantifiable and collapses to a single result. Many potential realities: only one gets actualized.

In 2.6.2, when time allows, the discussion can move onto application examples, with emphasis probably on strategy, war, competition, and where possible interactions with business and operations research, and science. Moreover, there can be a cross test of other hypotheses. This first sub-paper is merely a list of defining characteristics of the MIMS.

⁹ Example: phalanx, or baguazhang

¹⁰ Most specifically problems demonstrated in losses: the Spanish Armada, Pearl Harbor, Thermopylae, Red Cliff, etc.

¹¹ From ancient days, electricity in the air before storms, as before battles, were described as tension and the anger of God. This seems not too on the nose, since after all PEMC describes the mechanism of this, including through bioelectricity.

¹² The question is whether or not the layers are arranged correctly, or by order of importance and recursion from layer 1 down. Notice some of the internal harmonics which give some indication of model resilience.

References

1. "The Art of War," S. Tzu (transl by L. Giles)
2. "The Propensity of Things," F. Jullien, 1995
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4. "Calculating the Innate Shi, using the US as a Template," R. Careaga, 2019
5. "Asymmetric Vulnerabilities of the US and New Capabilities in Geopolitical Warfare, Including Economic, Digital, Cyberspatial, and Lawfare," R. Careaga, 2020
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